

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Influences of seasons, tissue types and locations on endophytic fungi diversity associated with *Terminalia bellirica* (Gaertn.) Roxb.

Samrat Tripura^{1*}, Prasenjit Debbarma^{1,2}, Suman Paul³, Rahul Saha¹, Badal Kumar Datta³, Ajay Krishna Saha¹

¹Mycology and Plant Pathology Laboratory, Department of Botany, Tripura University, Suryamaninagar, Tripura- 799022, India

²Department of Botany, Netaji Subhash Mahavidyalaya, Dhwanjanagar-799120, Udaipur, Tripura, India

³Plant Taxonomy and Biodiversity Laboratory, Department of Botany, Tripura University, Suryamaninagar, Tripura - 799022, India

*Corresponding author email: samrat.botany@tripurauniv.in

Article No.: STUJBR78B; Received: 02.03.2024; Peer-reviewed: 20.10.2024; Accepted: 14.11.2024; Published: 31.12.2024

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14892438>

Abstract

Terminalia bellirica is a traditional medicine plant used in various parts of the world. It has several properties, such as antimicrobial, and antioxidant, boosts immunity, regulates diabetes, and treats asthma, etc. Endophytic fungi reside within the plant tissue without causing plant disease symptoms. Endophytic fungi produce secondary metabolites that might play a pivotal role in conferring these pharmacological activities. Therefore, the present study was performed to unearth the novel endophytic fungi with seasonal influence from *T. bellirica*. A total of 643 endophytic fungal isolates were recovered from the leaves, barks, and roots of *T. bellirica* in three different seasons and identified at morphological levels. During the study, 26 culturable endophytic fungi including the non-sporulating forms belonging to 14 genera, 8 families, and 4 classes, were obtained. Ascomycota was found to be dominant (93%) and Mucoromycota (2%) was the least. The maximum isolate belongs to Sordariomycetes showing 47%. The isolation rate was found maximum in the root segments (0.62), while the colonization rate was recorded highest in the leaves (100%). However, the fungal endophytes were recovered maximum at Suryamaninagar (S1) site (180) followed by Debasthal (S5) site (147) and the least isolates were recovered at Ampinagar (S3) site (100). During the summer season, the highest total colonization frequency (CF) was detected by *Aspergillus niger* (124%) and *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* in monsoon (156%) and winter seasons (92%). The maximum fungal isolates were obtained during the monsoon season (286) followed by the summer (202) and winter seasons (155). The colonization rate was higher during the monsoon season as compared to winter and summer, whereas the maximum isolation rate was recorded during the monsoon (0.76) than summer (0.54) and winter (0.41) seasons, respectively. The type of tissue, sampling locations, and seasons influences the endophytic fungal diversity and composition in this plant. Species diversity of endophytic fungi was found to be maximum during the monsoon season and minimum during the winter. The endophytic fungi recovered from this plant might be further explored for their biological activities, anticancer drugs, pharmaceutical and agricultural fertilizers, and may be used commercially.

Keywords: *Terminalia bellirica*; Medicinal Plant; Endophytic Fungi; Tissue Specificity; Diversity

1. Introduction

Fungi are one of the most diverse life forms in the planet Earth. The term “endophytes” was first used by Anton de Bary in 1866 for those fungi colonizing inside the living plant tissues. Fossil evidence of many plants indicated that plants have been associated with endophytic fungi for >400 million years (De Bary, 1866; Hardoim et al., 2015; Chetia et al., 2019). These fungi inhabit host plant tissues during a certain period of their life cycle and do not cause obvious disease symptoms to the host plant organs (Verma et al., 2021). They usually exist in various aquatic and terrestrial plants (Sarasan et al., 2017; Cosoveanu and Cabrera, 2018). The symbiotic relationship of fungal endophytes with the host plant benefitted against natural enemies such as pathogens and herbivores (Schardl et al., 2004; Singh et al., 2011); increased the resistance of plants to abiotic stress factors such as salinity and heavy metal toxicity in soil (Khan et al., 2014) and even promotes plant growth (Hamayun et al., 2010). Some of the endophytes are capable of producing bioactive compounds similar to the host plant. These bioactive compounds exhibited a wide range of applications in the fields of agriculture and medicine (Wu et al., 2013). Endophytic fungi are reported to produce a variety of

secondary metabolites inside the plant tissues (Agusta, 2009). These metabolites from endophytic fungi showed important biological activities such as antibacterial, antioxidant, anticancer, immunomodulatory, antiviral, antituberculosis, anti-parasite, and insecticides (Hussain et al., 2014; Praptiwi et al., 2018).

Medicinal plants have become essential for treating several diseases originating from long-established practices of traditional medicine (Firenzuoli and Gori, 2007). The preparations of medicinal plants have eventually become an integral part of mainstream medicine after many ethnobotanicals and ethnopharmacological studies. Medicinal plants have formed a positive relationship with microbes in due course of evolution (Field et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2019). A reciprocal symbiotic relationship was found between endophytic fungi and host medicinal plants (Manganyi and Ateba, 2020). Endophytic fungi play a crucial role in enhancing resistance to abiotic stress in medicinal plants (Jia et al., 2016), improving secondary metabolism (Zhai et al., 2017), producing active ingredients (Ming et al., 2012), and promoting growth (Ye et al., 2020). Endophytic fungi have had a considerable impact on medicine, agriculture, and industry (Salehi and Safaie, 2024).

Figure 1. Map represents the collection sites of *T. bellirica* sample in different regions of Tripura.

Terminalia bellirica (Gaertn.) Roxb. belongs to the family Combretaceae, found to grow in Nepal, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, and Southeast Asia (Ramesh et al., 2005). Vernacularly it is known as “Bahera” or Beleric or Myrobalan. The fruit of this medicinal plant is one of the major constituents of the ayurvedic remedy Triphala. *T. bellirica* is used to shield the liver, lower cholesterol levels in the body, and also used in the treatment of digestive as well as respiratory disorders (Latha and Daisy, 2011). This plant is a good antioxidant and lowers glucose levels due to the presence of polyphenolic compounds like gallic acid, tannins, flavones, etc. (Nampootheri et al., 2011). The aqueous extract of *T. bellirica* fruits is used for the synthesis of zinc, iron, and copper oxide nanoparticles that are good biological and pharmaceutical agents to fight against different pathogens (Akhter et al., 2019). Various authors reported on the diversity of endophytic fungi derived from medicinal plants. However, as of now, no data is available on fungal diversity

associated with *T. bellirica*. Therefore, the present investigation was carried out to find out the influence of seasons, tissues, and locations on the colonization of culturable endophytic fungi within this plant. The present study also represented the species composition and distribution of culturable endophytic fungi inside the internal tissues of *T. bellirica*. This could pave the way for the discovery of new endophytic fungi that could have the potential to synthesize useful bioactive compounds.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites and sample collection

Tripura is a small state located in the northeastern part of India and has a rich biodiversity. Healthy and mature plant samples were randomly collected from different collection sites viz. Suryamaninagar, Bishalgarh, Ampinagar, Hathai Kotor, and Debasthal during summer, monsoon, and winter seasons from January 2021 to December 2022 (Table 2; Figure 1). The distance of the collected plants was maintained at least 10–25 km away from each of the study sites. The plant samples were collected from different parts, namely the leaf, bark, and root of *T. bellirica* (Table 1). However, the root parts were collected from a depth of 10–20 cm beneath the ground using the iron toolbar. The samples were collected separately in pre-sterilized polythene bags and the collected samples were brought to the laboratory. It was then processed for the isolation of endophytic fungi within 24 hours of collection. A herbarium specimen (voucher No. TUH-2386) (Figure 2) of the plant sample was submitted to the Herbarium Centre in the Department of Botany, Tripura University for future reference.

2.2. Isolation and identification of endophytic fungi

The collected plant samples were washed thoroughly in running tap water to remove the debris and dust from the surface of the tissues. A total of 1125 plant samples of different tissues were dissected separately. Subsequently, it was processed for surface sterilization as follows: Leaf, bark, and root samples were surface sterilized by dissolving into 70% ethanol (1 min), 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (30 sec) and 70% ethanol (30 sec) and were rinsed with sterilized distilled water nearly for 3 minutes (3 times), then allowed to surface dry under sterile conditions. The leaves were punched into circular segments (about 0.5 mm diameter) with the help of a sterile borer,

Figure 2. *Terminalia bellirica*. a. Natural habitat of the growing plant, b. Herbarium specimen (No. TUH-2386). Emergence colonies of endophytic fungi from different tissues of *T. bellirica* (c. Leaves, d. Bark and e. Root).

Figure 3. Isolation rate of endophytic fungi associated with *T. bellirica* across the tissues, site and seasons.

Figure 4. Colonization rate of endophytic fungi associated with *T. bellirica* across the tissues, site and seasons.

whereas bark tissues were cut into short pieces (5-6 cm long) and then the roots were excised into 4-5 cm long using the sterile blade (Suryanarayanan and Vijaykrishna, 2001) with minor modifications. The excised plant tissues were placed onto a Malt Extract Agar (MEA) medium supplemented with antibiotic streptomycin (500 mg L⁻¹) and subsequently sealed with parafilm. The petri plates were incubated at 28±1°C for 3-5 days and regularly observed for fungal growth. Individual hyphal tips that emerged from the edges of each plate were transferred separately onto fresh MEA plates. The pure fungal cultures were transferred onto the MEA slant and used for further

experiments. The pure endophytic fungal culture growing individually onto the fresh MEA medium was picked up using sterile needles and observed on the slide with the help of lactophenol cotton blue reagent under the Leica DM 750 microscope at 20X, 40X, and 100X magnifications. The isolates were identified based on their morphological and microscopic features, such as colony colour, texture, growth rate, hyphal structure, pigmentations, fungal spore morphology, and reproductive structures with the help of standard manual and texts (Ellis, 1971; Domsch et al., 1980; Watanabe, 2002).

2.3 Statistical analysis

The collected data was subjected to statistical analysis to understand the diversity of endophytic fungi associated with *T. bellirica*. The colonization rate, isolation rate, colonization frequency, and relative species frequency were calculated as per the formulae given below. In addition, the diversity indices including Shannon index (H'), Simpson's dominance (D), Simpson's diversity index ($1-D$), Fisher's alpha diversity index (a), Berger-Parker dominance (B), Brillouin index (HB) and Pielou evenness (J) were determined using R statistical software version 4.2.0 (R Core Team, 2022) to

figure out the diversity of the endophytic fungal isolates between three different tissues, sites and three seasons.

Colonization rate (CR %) (Pettrini et al., 1982)

$$CR \% = \frac{\text{Total number of plant-tissue segments infected by one or more fungi}}{\text{Total number of inoculated segments}} \times 100$$

Isolation rate (IR) (Wang and Guo, 2007)

$$IR = \frac{\text{Number of isolates obtained from plant tissue segments}}{\text{Total number of segments inoculated}}$$

Colonization frequency (CF %) (Fisher and Petrini, 1987)

CF % = (Number of segments colonized by each fungus) / (Total number of segments inoculated) × 100

Relative frequency (RF %) (Huang et al., 2008)

RF % = (Number of isolates of a species) / (Total number of isolates) × 100

3. Results

3.1 Isolation and identification of endophytic fungi

A total of 643 endophytic isolates were obtained from 1125 plant segments of *T. bellirica* collected from five different localities. Of these, 228, 182, and 233 isolates were recovered from leaves, barks, and roots, respectively (Table 3). The maximum colonization rate occurred in leaf tissues (100%), followed by barks (94.67%) and roots (93.07%). The isolation rate of fungal isolates was found maximum in the root (0.62), followed by leaves (0.61) and barks (0.49). A significant effect of host tissues was noticed on the colonization of endophytic fungi (Table 3).

Plant samples collected from Suryamaninagar (S1) have shown maximum recovery of endophytes (180 isolates) followed by Debasthal (S5) (147), Hathai Kotor (S4) (113), Bishalgarh (S2) (103), and the lowest was from Ampinagar (S3) (100) (Figure 2). The maximum colonization rate occurred in S1 and S4 (100%) followed by S2 (97.33%), and least was recorded in S3 and S5 (91.11%). The isolation rate was maximum in S1 (0.80), whereas the lowest was recorded in S3 (0.44). The maximum endophytic fungal isolates were recovered during the monsoon season (286) followed by summer (202) and the lowest were observed in the winter season (155). The highest colonization rate was during monsoon followed by winter and summer; however, the maximum isolation rate was recorded in

monsoon (0.76) followed by summer (0.54) and winter (0.41) respectively (Figure 3 and 4).

From *T. bellirica*, 26 endophytic fungal species were identified, belonging to 14 genera, 12 families, and 4 classes, along with 4 sterile mycelia morphotypes. A total of 26 endophytic fungal isolates were obtained along with four non-sporulating forms (Table 2). Among the isolates, twenty-two fungal isolates were obtained from leaves including the three non-sporulating forms; twenty fungal isolates were recovered from barks with the three non-sporulating forms, whereas root harbored twenty-six fungal isolates including the four non-sporulating forms. Out of these, Ascomycota was found to be dominant (93%), followed by non-sporulating forms (5%) and Mucoromycota (2%) (Figure 6). The isolated endophytic fungi were divided into five major classes namely Euromycetes, Dothideomycetes, Sordariomycetes, Mucoromycetes, and Sterile mycelia, and the maximum isolates belonged to Sordariomycetes (47%) (Figure 7).

The most fungal genera obtained from the *T. bellirica* were as follows: *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Chaetomium* sp., *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Corynespora torulosa*, *Diaporthe* sp., *Fusarium decemcellulare*, *Fusarium falciforme*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium solani*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, *Mucor* sp., *Nigrospora* sp., *Penicillium exsudans*, *Penicillium* sp. 1, *Penicillium* sp. 2, *Pestalotiopsis* sp., *Talaromyces australis*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Trichoderma* sp., and the sterile mycelia which did not sporulate (Figure 5). *Aspergillus niger*, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Corynespora torulosa*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, *Penicillium exsudans* were the most dominant species of endophytic fungi associated with *T. bellirica*.

Figure 5. Endophytic fungus isolated from three different tissues viz. leaf, bark, root of *T. bellirica*. a. *Alternaria alternata*, b. *Aspergillus niger*, c. *Aspergillus flavus*, d. *Aspergillus fumigatus*, e. *Corynespora torulosa*, f. *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, g. *Fusarium falciforme*, h. *Fusarium solani*, i. *Fusarium decemcellulare*, j. *Fusarium oxysporum*, k. *Mucor* sp., l. *Penicillium* sp. 2, m. *Pestalotiopsis* sp., n. *Trichoderma* sp., o. Non-sporulating groups I. Scale bar: a-d, h, j, k, and n = 40μm; e-g, i, l, m and o = 20μm.

Figure 6. Occurrence of endophytic fungal phylum associated with *T. bellirica*.

3.2. Effect of colonization frequency on tissues, sites and seasons

The results showed that the season affected the colonization of endophytic fungi communities in the sampling sites (Table 4). During the summer season, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Nigrospora* sp., non-sporulating groups (NS Gr. I, NS Gr. II and NS Gr. IV) were found confined to one site, whereas *Diaporthe* sp., *Fusarium falciforme*, *Penicillium* sp. 2, *Pestalotiopsis* sp., and *Talaromyces australis* were observed in two sites. However, *Corynespora torulosa* and *Lasiodiplodia theobromae* exist in all five sites (Table 5). In the case of monsoon season, *Aspergillus niger* and NS Gr. III occurred only at one site, whereas *Chaetomium* sp., *Nigrospora* sp., *Penicillium* sp. 3, NS Gr. II, NS Gr. IV was found in two sites. In addition, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Corynespora torulosa*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium solani*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, *Trichoderma harzianum* are present in all the study sites (Table 6). During the winter season, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Mucor* sp., *Nigrospora* sp., *Penicillium* sp. 3, *Pestalotiopsis* sp. *Talaromyces australis*, *Trichoderma* sp., NS Gr. II, NS Gr. III were present at one site, whereas *Chaetomium* sp., *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium solani*, *Fusarium falciforme*, NS Gr. I was recorded on two sites. But *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* and *Diaporthe* sp. were present in all study sites (Table 7). The present study showed that season influenced the composition of endophytic fungi within the host plants. Therefore, some endophytic fungal taxa were reported in only one or two seasons. For instance, *Penicillium* sp. 3 was exclusively reported during winter, whereas *Alternaria alternata* and NS Gr. IV were recorded in the summer and winter seasons and the rest of the isolates were reported in all the seasons. None of the *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Penicillium* sp. 3 and NS Gr. IV was obtained from the leaves and barks, whereas *Fusarium falciforme* was absent in the leaf sample. However, *Mucor* sp., *Nigrospora* sp., *Pestalotiopsis* sp. was devoid of bark.

Overall, the total colonization frequency was recorded maximum in the monsoon season, followed by summer, and winter. The overall percent of colonization frequency (CF) was shown by *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Corynespora torulosa*, and non-sporulating mycelia IV was the lowest. During the summer season, the maximum colonization frequency was observed in *Aspergillus niger*, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae* and the lowest occurred in *Nigrospora* sp., NS Gr. II and NS Gr. IV (Table 5). In monsoon, however, the colonization frequency was highest in *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Fusarium decemcellulare*, and *Penicillium* sp. 2, and the lowest was observed in NS Gr. III (Table 6). During the winter season, the highest colonization frequency was noticed in *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Corynespora torulosa* *Diaporthe* sp., and the lowest occurred in *Mucor* sp., *Pestalotiopsis* sp., *Talaromyces australis*, and NS Gr. III (Table 7). The maximum relative frequency (RF) was recorded in *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, followed by *Aspergillus niger*, *Corynespora torulosa*, and the lowest RF value was found in NS Gr. IV (Table 8).

Figure 7. Pie chart showing the different classes of endophytic fungi isolated from *T. bellirica*.

3.3. Diversity analysis of endophytic fungi

The endophytic fungal diversity varied significantly among different tissue types (Table 9). The Shannon diversity index, Simpson's (1-D), Pilon evenness (J), Fisher alpha, and Brillouin diversity index were highest in the root tissues followed by leaf tissues, and the lowest was observed in the bark. A notable influence of season on the endophytic fungal diversity was recorded. It was observed that the Fisher alpha diversity was higher during the winter season compared to the summer season, whereas the Shannon, Simpson, Pilon evenness (J), and Dominance (D) data showed higher values during the summer. Significant variation was also observed during the diversity analysis considering several locations of Tripura, Northeast, India (Table 9).

4. Discussion

In the present study a greater diversity of endophytic fungi was observed in different plant parts of *Terminalia bellirica*, a medicinally important plant collected from different locations of Tripura, Northeast-India. Isolation of endophytic fungi from medicinal plants gives an idea about their distribution in different tissues irrespective of geographic locations and various seasonal climatic conditions. This study recorded a higher endophytic fungal composition recovery from leaf tissues compared to bark and root tissues, which is in correspondence with the previous findings (Gond et al., 2012; Yu et al., 2018; Crasta and Anandrao, 2024). Higher colonization of endophytes in the leaf tissues could be due to exposure to wider surface area, rich nutrition, thin walls of leaves to external environment and also higher stomata rate on the abaxial surface that allow the fungal aerospores to enter inside (Lebron et al., 2002; Gond et al., 2012; Al-Harathi et al., 2023).

Our findings indicated that geographical location of *T. bellirica* influences the composition of endophytic fungi (Table 2). Several research studies have demonstrated that the degree of colonization may be influenced by site-specific factors (Carroll, 1995). The recovery of the endophytic fungal population was significantly affected by the sampling seasons in this study. The present study showed that the season influenced the composition of fungal endophytes in *T. bellirica*. Different selection pressures like pH, temperature and salinity acting on endophytes in different seasons within plant tissues are the primary determiners of the fluctuation of the species composition (Rodriguez et al., 2008; Kamalraj and Muthumary, 2013).

Most of the isolates belong to the phylum Ascomycota. The study conducted by several researchers also reported similar findings that most of the fungal isolates belong to the class Sordariomycetes and phylum Ascomycota (Gopane et al., 2021; Jahromi et al., 2021; Hatamzadeh et al., 2023; Crasta and Anandrao, 2024; Nongthombam et al., 2024). Vemireddy et al (2020) reported about rich fungal species colonized different tissues of *T. bellirica* and the fungal isolates represented in our study were also similar to their study. Some of the fungal isolates like *Colletotrichum*

gloeosporioides, *Lasiodiplodia*, and *Pestalotiopsis* were reported for the first time from *T. bellirica* that has been reported in other *Terminalia* species (Duong et al., 2006).

The variation in colonization frequency was also recorded across different collection sites. This variability may be due to the environmental attributes of the collection sites (Yadav et al., 2016). The distances between locations are the driving factor for increasing the likelihood of recovering diverse endophytic fungal species (Massimo et al., 2015). Several studies have shown that the seasons directly affect the composition of fungal communities and their colonization patterns (Kumar and Prasher, 2022). Our results showed that the fungal endophytes have recorded maximum during the monsoon season. It was reported that high moisture, temperature, and fluctuation of secondary metabolites expand the growth and dispersal of endophytic fungi spores during the monsoon seasons (Mishra et al., 2012; Fang et al., 2013). Tejesvi et al (2005) in their study on *Terminalia arjuna* reported about the rich endophytic fungal diversity during the monsoon season. On the contrary, several studies have noticed higher endophytic fungal diversity was in the winter season compared to rainy and summer seasons (Fang et al., 2013). In addition, a lower annual rainfall and temperature may influence the colonization of endophytes in host tissues (Sadeghi et al., 2019).

The results on diversity indices indicated that the seasons, tissues and sites affected the colonization and distribution of fungal endophytes associated with *T. bellirica*. The Simpson's diversity and Shannon-Wiener indices of endophytic fungi recovered from *Cymbidium aloifolium* have recorded the highest diversity values in root tissues that suggest the diversity of endophytic fungi varies within the host plant tissues and sites (Nisa et al., 2015). The variation in the endophytic diversity among sampling locations could be due to differences in micro-environment conditions, soil pH, host attributes, and agronomic practices at the studied sites (Jan et al., 2022). Fungal taxa spatially restricted distribution suggests that endophytic communities are spatially structured (Sadeghi et al., 2019). Environmental elements including temperature, humidity, and ecological niches impact endophyte variation and play a crucial role in the spread and success of endophytic fungal spore germination (Shannon and Weaver, 1963).

5. Conclusion

The present study revealed that the *T. bellirica* plant harbored diverse endophytic fungi. It was observed that different tissue types, host plant locations, and seasons influenced the endophytic fungal composition and diversity. A total of 643 endophytic fungal isolates were isolated from different tissues of *T. bellirica* across summer, monsoon, and winter seasons. The fungal isolates were identified using macroscopic and microscopic techniques. The most dominant species among the isolates were *Aspergillus niger*, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, *Corynespora torulosa*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, and *Penicillium exsudans*. The majority of the isolated ones belonged to the class Sordariomycetes of the phylum Ascomycota. Tissue specificity was observed in the endophytic fungi colonization on the host tissues. The maximum colonization of endophytic fungi was detected in Suryamaninagar (S1) as compared to the other study sites. During the summer season, the overall maximum colonization frequency was shown by *Aspergillus niger*; whereas *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* was observed highest during the monsoon and winter seasons. The diversity indices showed that the isolated endophytic fungi were highest during the monsoon season and lowest during the winter. This intricate web of interactions between the endophytic fungi and the host plant and/or the results of these interactions may be helpful in enhancing production and sustainability of *T. bellirica*.

Acknowledgements

All the authors are grateful to the Head of the Department, Department of Botany, Tripura University for providing the laboratory facilities during the tenure of the work. First author would like to acknowledge to the DBT Twinning Project, Govt. of India (Sanctioned Order No.: BT/PR25260/NER/95/1102/2017) for the fellowship and assisting the necessary facilities to carry out the research works. Authors would also like to thank Mr. Biplab Banik, Research Scholar, Plant Taxonomy and Biodiversity Laboratory,

Department of Botany, Tripura University, Tripura for the construction of the study sites map of Tripura, India.

Authors' contributions

ST and AKS perceived the idea and designed the experiments. ST, RS and PD conducted the field survey for sample collections. ST performed the experiments and prepared the initial manuscript. SP conducted the data analysis. PD, SP and AKS edited the draft and finalized the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflicts of interests

The authors clearly state that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- Afzal I, Shinwari ZK, Sikandar S and Shahzad S. 2019. Plant beneficial endophytic bacteria: Mechanisms, diversity, host range and genetic determinants. *Microbiological Research* 221: 36-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2019.02.001>
- Agusta A. 2009. Biologi dan kimia jamur endofit. Bandung: Institut Teknologi Bandung.
- Akhter SM, Mohammad F and Ahmad S. 2019. *Terminalia bellirica* mediated green synthesis of nanoparticles of copper, iron and zinc metal oxides as the alternate antibacterial agents against some common pathogens. *BioNanoScience* 9: 365-72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12668-019-0601-4>
- Al-Harhi HF, Elgorgan AM, Ahmed B, Bahkali AH, ElSheshtawi M, Shaik JP, Al-Falih AM and Syed A. 2023. Identification, molecular characterization, and plant growth promoting activities of endophytic fungi of *Jasminum sambac*, *Camellia sinensis*, and *Ocimum basilicum*. *Journal of King Saud University-Science* 35(3): 102558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2023.102558>
- Carroll G. 1995. Forest endophytes: pattern and process. *Canadian Journal of Botany* 73(S1): 1316-24.
- Chetia H, Kabiraj D, Bharali B, Ojha S, Barkataki MP, Saikia D, Singh T, Mosahari PV, Sharma P and Bora U. 2019. Exploring the benefits of endophytic fungi via omics. In: Singh, B. (eds) *Advances in Endophytic Fungal Research*. *Fungal Biology*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03589-1_4
- Cosoveanu A and Cabrera R. 2018. Endophytic fungi in species of *Artemisia*. *Journal of Fungi* 4(2): 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof4020053>
- Crasta GL, and Anandrao RK. 2024. Seasonal diversity & spatiotemporal distribution of fungal endophytes associated with the medicinal plant *Coleus forskohlii* Briq. *Plant Science Today* 11(1): 223-33. <https://doi.org/10.14719/pst.2729>
- De Bary A. 1866. *Morphologie und physiologie der pilze, flechten und myxomyceten*. Engelmann.
- Domsch KH, Gams W and Anderson TH. 1980. *Compendium of soil fungi*. Volume 1. Academic Press (London) Ltd.
- Duong LM, Jeewon R, Lumyong S and Hyde KD. 2006. DGGE coupled with ribosomal DNA gene phylogenies reveal uncharacterized fungal phylotypes. *Fungal Diversity* v 23: 121-138.
- Ellis MB. 1971. *Dematiaceous hypomycetes*. CAB International Mycological Institute, Kew, England.
- Fang W, Yang L, Zhu X, Zeng L and Li X. 2013. Seasonal and habitat dependent variations in culturable endophytes of *Camellia sinensis*. *Journal of Plant Pathology and Microbiology* 4(3): 2157-471. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7471.1000169>
- Field KJ, Bidartondo MI, Rimington WR, Hoysted GA, Beerling D, Cameron DD, Duckett JG, Leake JR and Pressel S. 2019. Functional complementarity of ancient plant–fungal mutualisms: contrasting nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon exchanges between Mucoromycotina and Glomeromycotina fungal symbionts of liverworts. *New Phytologist* 223(2): 908-21. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.15819>
- Firenzuoli F and Gori L. 2007. Herbal medicine today: clinical and research issues. *Evidence-based Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 4:37-40. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ecam/nem096>

Table 1. Details of medicinal plant collected from the Tripura, India.

Sl No.	Scientific name	Plant family	Plant parts	Voucher specimen	Uses	References
1.	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae	Leaves, barks, and roots	TUH-2386	Lower cholesterol and glucose levels, treat respiratory disorders. It is also used for good antioxidant, biological, pharmaceutical agents and synthesis of nanoparticles.	Latha and Daisy, 2011; Nampoothiri et al., 2011; Akhter et al., 2019

Table 2. Collection ID, GPS coordinates, soil pH, soil temperature and soil moisture of the sampling sites in Tripura, India.

Location	Suryamaninagar (S1)	Bishalgarh (S2)	Ampinagar (S3)	Hathai Kotor (S4)	Debasthal (S5)
Longitude	23°45'45"N	23°40'06"N	23°40'33"N	23°48'56"N	24°19'13"N
Latitude	91°15'51"E	91°18'11"E	91°37'54"E	91°34'48"E	92°03'36"E
Altitude (m)	41	54	64	121	94
Soil pH	7	6.8	6.5	7.5	7.5
Soil temperature	26.5°C	28°C	22°C	27°C	20°C
Soil moisture	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.07
*Forest types	Moist deciduous mixed forest	Sal forest	Moist deciduous mixed forest	Garjan forest	Evergreen forest

*Forest types – Source: India State of Forest Report (ISFR 2021).

Table 3. Isolation rate (IR) and percentage of colonization rate (CR) of *T. bellirica*.

	No. of segments inoculated	No. of segments infected	No. of isolates obtained	IR	CR %
Leaf	375	375	228	0.61	100
Bark	375	355	182	0.49	94.67
Root	375	349	233	0.62	93.07
S1	225	225	180	0.80	100
S2	225	219	103	0.46	97.33
S3	225	205	100	0.44	91.11
S4	225	225	113	0.50	100
S5	225	205	147	0.65	91.11
Summer	375	345	202	0.54	92
Monsoon	375	375	286	0.76	100
Winter	375	359	155	0.41	95.73

Note: S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal.

Table 4. Occurrence of endophytic fungi of *T. bellirica* collected from different tissues, sites and seasons.

Fungal isolates	L	B	R	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	Summer	Monsoon	Winter
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Corynespora torulosa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Diaporthe</i> sp.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Penicillium exsudans</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 1	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 2	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+
<i>Pestalotiopsis</i> sp.	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
<i>Talaromyces australis</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
NS Gr. I	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
NS Gr. II	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+
NS Gr. III	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
NS Gr. IV	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-

Note: L= Leaves, B= Bark, R= Root, S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S3- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal. NS Gr. = Non-sporulating groups.

Table 5. Percent (CF) Colonization frequency of endophytic fungi in different tissues of *Terminalia bellirica* in summer season.

Fungal isolates	S1			S2			S3			S4			S5			Total CF
	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	4	16
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	20
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	4	12	20	0	0	0	8	4	0	4	20	8	4	28	12	124
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	0	8	0	0	24
<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	20	24	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	4	0	4	8	0	100
<i>Corynespora torulosa</i>	4	0	0	20	0	0	4	0	8	8	8	0	12	0	0	64
<i>Diaporthe</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	8	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	0	16	4	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	32
<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	16	0	0	0	24
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	8	8	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	32
<i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i>	0	0	8	8	20	0	8	0	0	8	0	4	12	0	16	84
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	12	0	0	20
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
<i>Penicillium exsudans</i>	12	0	0	0	0	8	0	8	4	0	0	12	0	0	0	44
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 1	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Pestalotiopsis</i> sp.	8	0	0	12	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28
<i>Talaromyces australis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	8
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	0	8	24	0	0	12	0	0	4	0	8	8	0	0	8	72
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	0	0	16	28
NS Gr. I	8	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
NS Gr. II	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
NS Gr. III	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	16
NS Gr. IV	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Total	72	88	72	40	48	60	28	16	48	52	48	56	80	36	64	808

Note: L= Leaves, B= Bark, R= Root, S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal. NS Gr. = Non-sporulating groups.

Table 6. Percent (CF) Colonization frequency of endophytic fungi in different tissues of *Terminalia bellirica* in monsoon season.

Fungal isolates	S1			S2			S3			S4			S5			Total CF
	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	0	4	0	0	0	8	0	0	8	0	8	0	0	0	0	28
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	0	4	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	28
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	16
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	0	8	12	0	4	8	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	12	16	72
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	16
<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	28	24	0	12	0	8	16	0	12	0	8	8	16	24	0	156
<i>Corynespora torulosa</i>	32	0	12	0	0	4	4	0	0	4	0	0	28	0	0	84
<i>Diaporthe</i> sp.	20	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	4	20	0	4	64
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	4	28	4	0	0	0	8	4	0	8	4	0	0	36	0	96
<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	12
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	0	4	0	0	16	0	0	4	36
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	12	28
<i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i>	4	32	4	4	0	0	0	0	4	12	0	0	16	0	0	76
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	20
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	12
<i>Penicillium exsudans</i>	8	12	4	0	0	0	8	16	4	0	16	8	0	0	0	76
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 1	12	4	0	16	20	20	12	0	4	0	0	0	0	4	0	92
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 2	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	12
<i>Pestalotiopsis</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	4	8	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	20
<i>Talaromyces australis</i>	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	8	24
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	0	8	0	12	0	0	20	8	0	0	16	0	0	8	12	84
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4	4	16
NS Gr. I	4	12	0	0	0	4	4	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	32
NS Gr. II	4	0	12	0	0	0	4	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	28
NS Gr. III	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4
NS Gr. IV	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	12
Total	120	140	88	44	24	84	88	40	68	32	56	80	88	88	104	1144

Note: L= Leaves, B= Bark, R= Root, S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal. NS Gr. = Non-sporulating groups.

Table 7. Percent (CF) Colonization frequency of endophytic fungi indifferent tissues of *Terminalia bellirica* in winter season.

Fungal isolates	S1			S2			S3			S4			S5			Total CF
	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	L	B	R	
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	0	0	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	12
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	4	0	0	36
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	12
<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	16	0	0	12	20	0	16	0	0	20	0	0	4	0	4	92
<i>Corynespora torulosa</i>	0	8	4	0	20	0	0	0	0	4	12	8	12	0	4	72
<i>Diaporthe</i> sp.	8	0	4	20	0	0	4	0	0	16	0	0	4	0	8	64
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	8	0	0	0	0	8	0	4	12	0	12	0	0	0	0	44
<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	8
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	8	20
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	4	16
<i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i>	8	0	8	0	0	0	8	0	0	8	4	0	0	4	0	40
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	8
<i>Penicillium exsudans</i>	0	0	0	0	0	8	8	16	8	0	4	8	0	8	0	60
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 1	0	4	0	0	0	0	20	0	4	0	0	0	12	0	0	40
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 2	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
<i>Pestalotiopsis</i> sp.	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
<i>Talaromyces australis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	0	4	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	28
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
NS Gr. I	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	4	16
NS Gr. II	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
NS Gr. III	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
NS Gr. IV	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	52	20	68	40	44	28	68	20	24	52	40	36	56	20	52	620

Note: L= Leaves, B= Bark, R= Root, S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal. NS Gr. = Non-sporulating groups.

Table 8. Relative frequency (RF) of endophytic fungi in different sites and seasons of *Terminalia bellirica*

Fungal isolates	Tissues			Locations					Seasons			Total	RF
	L	B	R	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	Summer	Monsoon	Winter		
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	3	3	5	1	2	2	3	3	4	7	0	11	1.71
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	2	1	11	7	2	0	1	4	5	7	2	14	2.18
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	1	3	5	1	2	4	1	1	2	4	3	9	1.40
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8	24	26	20	3	5	11	19	31	18	9	58	9.02
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	6	1	6	4	2	1	2	4	6	4	3	13	2.02
<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	46	33	8	28	18	11	15	15	25	39	23	87	13.53
<i>Corynespora torulosa</i>	33	12	10	15	11	4	11	14	16	21	18	55	8.55
<i>Diaporthe</i> sp.	27	2	6	9	7	3	7	9	3	16	16	35	5.44
<i>Fusarium decemcellulare</i>	7	27	9	16	4	7	7	9	8	24	11	43	6.69
<i>Fusarium falciforme</i>	0	2	7	1	1	3	1	3	4	3	2	9	1.40
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	0	0	20	1	3	2	11	3	6	9	5	20	3.11
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	7	3	9	6	2	1	1	9	8	7	4	19	2.95
<i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i>	24	15	11	16	8	5	9	12	21	19	10	50	7.78
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	4	0	7	0	3	0	3	5	5	5	1	11	1.71
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	3	0	3	0	2	0	0	4	1	3	2	6	0.93
<i>Penicillium exsudans</i>	9	20	16	9	4	18	12	2	11	19	15	45	6.998
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 1	18	9	8	6	14	11	0	4	2	23	10	35	5.44
<i>Penicillium</i> sp. 2	0	0	5	3	0	0	0	2	0	3	2	5	0.78
<i>Pestalotiopsis</i> sp.	8	0	5	3	6	2	2	0	7	5	1	13	2.02
<i>Talaromyces australis</i>	1	2	6	1	0	4	1	3	2	6	1	9	1.40
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	8	15	23	11	8	8	8	11	18	21	7	46	7.15
<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	4	4	6	2	0	3	3	6	7	4	3	14	2.18
NS Gr. I	6	4	6	9	1	2	1	3	4	8	4	16	2.49
NS Gr. II	2	2	6	7	0	3	0	0	1	7	2	10	1.56
NS Gr. III	1	0	5	2	0	1	1	2	4	1	1	6	0.93
NS Gr. IV	0	0	4	2	0	0	2	0	1	3	0	4	0.62
Total	228	182	233	180	103	100	113	147	202	286	155	643	

Note: L= Leaves, B= Bark, R= Root, S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debasthal. NS Gr. = Non-sporulating groups.

Table 9. The diversity indices of isolated endophytic fungi of *Terminalia bellirica* based on and tissue, location and season.

Diversity indices	Tissues			Locations					Seasons		
	Leaves	Bark	Root	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	Summer	Monsoon	Winter
Species richness (<i>S</i>)	22	20	26	24	21	21	22	24	25	26	24
Shannon (<i>H'</i>)	2.5887	2.4682	3.0883	2.7857	2.6708	2.7402	2.7162	2.8772	2.9463	2.8262	2.7795
Simpson (<i>1-D</i>)	0.8973	0.8929	0.9455	0.9227	0.9115	0.9168	0.9200	0.9318	0.9349	0.9225	0.9212
Pilou evenness (<i>J</i>)	0.2974	0.3048	0.3063	0.2851	0.2818	0.2991	0.3102	0.2973	0.3056	0.2910	0.2918
Dominance (<i>D</i>)	0.0987	0.1021	0.0504	0.0722	0.0796	0.0739	0.0717	0.0618	0.0730	0.0618	0.0728
Fisher alpha (<i>a</i>)	6.0069	5.3407	7.4966	7.4374	7.4003	8.1068	8.1517	7.6503	7.5111	6.9494	7.9446
Berger-Parker (<i>B</i>)	0.2018	0.1813	0.1116	0.1556	0.1748	0.1800	0.1327	0.1293	0.1535	0.1364	0.1484
Brillouin (<i>HB</i>)	2.4282	2.3012	2.8863	2.5768	2.3915	2.4416	2.4440	2.6297	2.6249	2.7814	2.5457

Note: S1- Suryamaninagar, S2- Bishalgarh, S3- Ampinagar, S4- Hathai Kotor, S5- Debastha

- Fisher PJ and Petrini O. 1987. Location of fungal endophytes in tissues of *Suaeda frutescens*: a preliminary study. *Transactions of the British Mycological Society* 89(2): 246-9.
- Gond SK, Mishra A, Sharma VK, Verma SK, Kumar J, Kharwar RN and Kumar A. 2012. Diversity and antimicrobial activity of endophytic fungi isolated from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, a well-known medicinal plant of India. *Mycoscience* 53(2): 113-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10267-011-0146-Z>
- Gopane B, Tchatchouang CK, Regnier T, Ateba CN and Manganyi MC. 2021. Community diversity and stress tolerance of culturable endophytic fungi from black seed (*Nigella sativa* L.). *South African Journal of Botany* 137: 272-277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2020.10.026>
- Hamayun M, Khan SA, Khan AL, Rehman G, Kim YH, Iqbal I, Hussain J, Sohn EY and Lee IJ. 2010. Gibberellin production and plant growth promotion from pure cultures of *Cladosporium* sp. MH-6 isolated from cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.). *Mycologia* 102 (5): 989-95. <https://doi.org/10.3852/09-261>
- Hardoim PR, Van Overbeek LS, Berg G, Pirttilä AM, Compant S, Campisano A, Döring M and Sessitsch A. 2015. The hidden world within plants: ecological and evolutionary considerations for defining functioning of microbial endophytes. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews* 79(3): 293-320. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mmr.00050-14>
- Hatamzadeh S, Rahnama K, White JF, Oghaz NA, Nasrollahnejad S, Hemmati K. 2023. Investigation of some endophytic fungi from five medicinal plants with growth promoting ability on maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Journal of Applied Microbiology* 134(1): lxaco15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jambio/lxaco15>
- Huang WY, Cai YZ, Hyde KD, Corke H and Sun M. 2008. Biodiversity of endophytic fungi associated with 29 traditional Chinese medicinal plants. *Fungal Diversity* 33: 61-75.
- Hussain H, Kliche-Spory C, Al-Harrasi A, Al-Rawahi A, Abbas G, Green IR, Schulz B, Krohn K and Shah A. 2014. Antimicrobial constituents from three endophytic fungi. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine* 7: S224-7. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1995-7645\(14\)60236-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1995-7645(14)60236-4)
- Jahromi MS, Azizi A and Soltani J. 2021. Diversity and spatiotemporal distribution of fungal endophytes associated with *Salvia multicaulis*. *Current Microbiology* 78: 1432-47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-021-02430-y>
- Jan B, Reshi ZA and Mohiddin FA. 2022. Site and organ-specific culture-dependent endophytic diversity of *Crocus sativus* L. (saffron) in Kashmir Himalaya, India. *Microbial Ecology* 83(4): 989-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-021-01817-5>
- Jia M, Chen L, Xin HL, Zheng CJ, Rahman K, Han T and Qin LP. 2016. A friendly relationship between endophytic fungi and medicinal plants: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 7: 906. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.00906>
- Kamalraj S and Muthumary J. 2013. Prevalence and seasonal periodicity of endophytic coelomycetous fungi in Tamil Nadu, India. *International Journal of Biodiversity Conservation* 5(8): 469-77.
- Khan AL, Waqas M, Hussain J, Al-Harrasi A and Lee IJ. 2014. Fungal endophyte *Penicillium janthinellum* LK5 can reduce cadmium toxicity in *Solanum lycopersicum* (Sitiens and Rhe). *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 50: 75-85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-013-0833-3>
- Kumar V and Prasher IB. 2022. Seasonal variation and tissues specificity of endophytic fungi of *Dillenia indica* L. and their extracellular enzymatic activity. *Archives of Microbiology* 204(6): 341. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00203-022-02933-7>
- Latha RC and Daisy P. 2011. Insulin-secretagogue, antihyperlipidemic and other protective effects of gallic acid isolated from *Terminalia bellirica* Roxb. in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Chemico-biological Interactions* 189(1-2): 112-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2010.11.005>
- Lebron I, Suarez DL and Yoshida T. 2002. Gypsum effect on the aggregate size and geometry of three sodic soils under reclamation. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 66(1): 92-8.
- Manganyi MC and Ateba CN. 2020. Untapped potentials of endophytic fungi: A review of novel bioactive compounds with biological applications. *Microorganisms* 8(12): 1934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8121934>
- Massimo NC, Nandi Devan MM, Arendt KR, Wilch MH, Riddle JM, Furr SH, Steen C, U'Ren JM, Sandberg DC and Arnold AE. 2015. Fungal endophytes in aboveground tissues of desert plants: infrequent in culture, but highly diverse and distinctive symbionts. *Microbial Ecology* 70: 61-76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-014-0563-6>
- Ming Q, Han T, Li W, Zhang Q, Zhang H, Zheng C, Huang F, Rahman K and Qin L. 2012. Tanshinone IIA and tanshinone I production by *Trichoderma atroviride* D16, an endophytic fungus in *Salvia miltiorrhiza*. *Phytomedicine* 19(3-4): 330-3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2011.09.076>
- Mishra A, Gond SK, Kumar A, Sharma VK, Verma SK, Kharwar RN and Sieber TN. 2012. Season and tissue type affect fungal endophyte communities of the Indian medicinal plant *Tinospora cordifolia* more strongly than geographic location. *Microbial Ecology* 64:388-98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-012-0029-7>
- Nampoothiri SV, Prathapan A, Cherian OL, Raghu KG, Venugopalan VV and Sundaresan A. 2011. In vitro antioxidant and inhibitory potential of *Terminalia bellirica* and *Emblca officinalis* fruits against LDL oxidation and key enzymes linked to type 2 diabetes. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 49(1): 125-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.10.006>
- Nisa H, Kamili AN, Nawchoo IA, Shafi S, Shameem N and Bandh SA. 2015. Fungal endophytes as prolific source of phytochemicals and other bioactive natural products: a review. *Microbial Pathogenesis* 82: 50-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2015.04.001>
- Nongthombam KS, Mutum SS and Pandey RR. 2024. Distribution, Diversity and Biochemical Analysis of Endophytic Fungi Associated with *Chromolaena odorata*. *Journal of Applied Life Sciences International* 27(1): 17-29. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jalsi/2024/v27i1634>
- Petrini O, Stone J and Carroll FE. 1982. Endophytic fungi in evergreen shrubs in western Oregon: a preliminary study. *Canadian Journal of Botany* 60(6):789-96.
- Praptiwi, Raunsai M, Wulansari D, Fathoni A and Agusta A. 2018. Antibacterial and antioxidant activities of endophytic fungi extracts from medicinal plant from Central Sulawesi. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* 8(08): 069-074. DOI: 10.7324/JAPS.2018.8811
- R Core Team. 2022. *R. A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Ramesh M, Umate P, Venugopal Rao K and Sadanandam A. 2005. Micropropagation of *Terminalia bellirica* Roxb.—a sericulture and medicinal plant. *In Vitro Cellular & Developmental Biology-Plant* 41: 320-3. <https://doi.org/10.1079/IVP2004626>
- Rodriguez RJ, Henson J, Van Volkenburgh E, Hoy M, Wright L, Beckwith F, Kim Y, Redman RS. 2008. Stress tolerance in plants via habitat-adapted symbiosis. *International Society of Microbial Ecology* 2: 404- 416. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2007.106>
- Sadeghi F, Samsampour D, Seyahooei MA, Bagheri A and Soltani J. 2019. Diversity and spatiotemporal distribution of fungal endophytes associated with *Citrus reticulata* cv. Siyadoo. *Current Microbiology* 76: 279-89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-019-01632-9>
- Salehi M, Safaie N. 2024. Endophytic fungi: secondary metabolites and plant biotic and abiotic stress management. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 29 (15): 1345210. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2024.1345210>
- Sarasan M, Puthumana J, Job N, Han J, Lee JS, Philip R. 2017. Marine algalicolous endophytic fungi—a promising drug resource of the era. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology* 27(6): 1039-1052. <https://doi.org/10.4014/jmb.1701.01036>
- Schardl CL, Leuchtman A and Spiering MJ. 2004. Symbioses of grasses with seedborne fungal endophytes. *Annual Review of Plant Biology* 55: 315-340. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.55.031903.141735>
- Shannon CE, Weaver W. 1963. *The mathematical theory of communication*. University of Illinois Press, Urbana.
- Singh DK, Sharma VK, Kumar J, Mishra A, Verma SK, Sieber TN and Kharwar RN. 2017. Diversity of endophytic mycobiota of tropical tree *Tectona grandis* Linn. f.: Spatiotemporal and tissue type effects. *Scientific Reports* 7(1): 3745. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-03933-0>
- Singh LP, Gill SS and Tuteja N. 2011. Unraveling the role of fungal symbionts in plant abiotic stress tolerance. *Plant signaling & behavior* 6(2): 175-91. <https://doi.org/10.4161/psb.6.2.14146>
- Suryanarayanan TS and Vijaykrishna D. 2001. Fungal endophytes of aerial roots of *Ficus benghalensis*. *Fungal Diversity* 8: 155-161.

Tejesvi MV, Mahesh B, Nalini MS, Prakash HS, Kini KR, Subbiah V and Shetty HS. 2005. Endophytic fungal assemblages from inner bark and twig of *Terminalia arjuna* W. & A. (Combretaceae). World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology 21: 1535-40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11274-005-7579-5>

Vemireddy B, Madasi A, Ajmeera A and Vanteru KR. 2020. Distribution and diversity of endophytic fungi associated with three medicinal tree species from Eturnagaram Wildlife Sanctuary, TS, India. Journal of Applied Biology and Biotechnology 8(6): 7-12. DOI: 10.7324/JABB.2020.80602

Verma SK, Sahu PK, Kumar K, Pal G, Gond SK, Kharwar RN and White JF. 2021. Endophyte roles in nutrient acquisition, root system architecture development and oxidative stress tolerance. Journal of Applied Microbiology 131 (5): 2161-77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.15111>

Wang Y and Guo LD. 2007. A comparative study of endophytic fungi in needles, bark, and xylem of *Pinus tabulaeformis*. Botany 85 (10): 911-7. <https://doi.org/10.1139/B07-084>

Watanabe, T. 2002. *Pictorial Atlas of Soil and Seed fungi: Morphologies of cultured fungi and key to species*. 2nd Ed. CRC Press Florida US.

Wu H, Yang HY, You XL and Li YH. 2013. Diversity of endophytic fungi from roots of *Panax ginseng* and their saponin yield capacities. Springer Plus 2(1): 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-1801-2-107>

Yadav M, Yadav A, Kumar S, Yadav JP. 2016. Spatial and seasonal influences on culturable endophytic mycobiota associated with different tissues of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam. and their antibacterial activity against MDR strains. BMC Microbiology 16(1): 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-016-0664-0>

Yan L, Zhu J, Zhao X, Shi J, Jiang C and Shao D. 2019. Beneficial effects of endophytic fungi colonization on plants. Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology 103: 3327-40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-019-09713-2>

Ye B, Wu Y, Zhai X, Zhang R, Wu J, Zhang C, Rahman K, Qin L, Han T and Zheng C. 2020. Beneficial effects of endophytic fungi from the *Anoectochilus* and *Ludisia* species on the growth and secondary metabolism of *Anoectochilus roxburghii*. ACS Omega 5(7): 3487-97. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.9b03789>

Yu J, Wu Y, He Z, Li M, Zhu K, Gao B. 2018. Diversity and antifungal activity of endophytic fungi associated with *Camellia oleifera*. Microbiology 46(2): 85-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12298093.2018.1454008>

Zhai X, Jia M, Chen L, Zheng CJ, Rahman K, Han T and Qin LP. 2017. The regulatory mechanism of fungal elicitor-induced secondary metabolite biosynthesis in medicinal plants. Critical Reviews in Microbiology 43(2): 238-61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1040841X.2016.1201041>

Zhang J, Lu J, Zhu Y, Shen X, Zhu B and Qin L. 2023. Roles of endophytic fungi in medicinal plant abiotic stress response and TCM quality development. Chinese Herbal Medicines 16 (2): 204-213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chmed.2023.02.006>

